

Animated Faces that Lie and Deceive

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[Animação · Animation]

Abstract

Lying and deceitful characters are a common means of building narrative tension and conflict, and can appear in a variety of roles. They are certainly no stranger to animated films, and these characters may lie through their dialogues or their singing, their body language or their facial expressions. The face plays a major role in the communication of lying and deceit, thus it will be the central focus in this discussion of lying animated characters. The development of acting and facial expressions over the decades is compared by discussing the most iconic lying character, Disney's Pinocchio from 1940, and lying animated characters in the 2D animated films Aladdin and Mulan, as well as the 3D animated films Rango and Zootopia. Differences are shown in how facial expressions are used in the animated performance to express lying and deceit. In addition, changes in the narrative complexity and psychology of the characters in the respective films have influence on the animated performance and expressions. In the field of psychology and behavior studies, Paul Ekman's focus on facial expressions has brought forth the Facial Action Coding System (FACS). This research into the structure of the muscles in the face and the resulting facial expressions has influenced contemporary high-end animated CG faces. Whether for cartoon or realistic characters, the absorption of Ekman's research into animation practice has enabled the creation of heightened realism within the acting performance. Another important factor in the creation of the animated facial performance is the chosen animation technique, such as 2D hand drawn or 3D computer animation.

Keywords

Character animation, performance, 2D animation, 3D animation, lies, FACS, storytelling

1. Introduction

Lying and deceitful characters often appear in animated films to create tension and conflict. Through their dialogue, singing, body language, and facial expressions, these characters are able to deceive and mislead their fellow cast members, adding suspense and intrigue to the plot. These characters may lie for a variety of reasons, from protecting those they care about to gaining power or wealth. These characters often have a hidden agenda and must be careful to keep their deception a secret. This adds

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an additional layer of complexity to the narrative, as the audience must try to unravel the truth behind the lies. At the same time, if there is no ambivalence purposefully intended in the characters performance, the animators need to ensure that the audience clearly understands if the animated character is lying or is being honest. To narrow down the scope of lying animated characters, this investigation leaves out characters that lie in song, as singing requires a different kind of animated performance. A singing performance tends to be focused on the delivery of the singing, and the character usually believes in what they sing, thus it is rarely intended to deceive. This investigation focuses on characters acting in scenes predominantly with dialogue. Further, the emphasis lies in the observation of the animated face, since much communication takes place through facial expressions.

The selection of animated films for closer analysis of lying characters is based on the following criteria: Firstly, feature films from major studios that have highly developed characters and stories, a very high craft level within the animated performance and one or more lies or lying characters within the plot. Secondly, films from different times (starting with Pinocchio) to observe a potential progression, and thirdly, different animation techniques (2D and 3D). The fourth criterion is films that use ambiguous and complex character personalities, and in which lies are of some significance to the story; thus results a stronger focus on more contemporary films. In a scene and acting analysis, the animated performances of the characters, the techniques and methods used for communicating lying through face and body language, as well as their evolution seen across the various films, will be discussed.

2. About Lying

A study by psychologists Bond and DePaulo showed that the average adult could only distinguish truth from falsehood 54 per cent of the time [1]. Former FBI agent and body language expert Joe Navarro adds from his experience “every time I hear somebody out there say, oh I can tell that they’re lying from their body language, I just say that’s absolute rubbish. There is no science to support it.” [2].

Science has yet to find a reliable way to accurately detect whether someone is lying or not. Many techniques, such as polygraphs, have been used to assess whether a person is being truthful, but these methods have proven to be unreliable and ineffective in detecting deception [3]. In addition, humans are not naturally good at detecting lies and deception, and even experts in the field are only slightly better than chance. As such, science has not yet found absolute guidelines and rules to uncover lies.

It is clear that actors are no liars, but professional performers who strive to portray characters truthfully and with integrity. In acting, as Paul Ekman observed, the „audience agrees to be misled, for a time” [4] that is why they watch the film.

For animators and storytellers, the question arises how to show lying in animated characters and in their acting. When creating animated characters that communicate lying and deception, it is important to consider

the context and how their actions will be interpreted. Animated characters should be able to convey the intended message well through their design and acting [5]. For example, when a character is lying, subtle body language and facial expressions can be used to emphasize feelings of deceit. Additionally, the dialogue can be crafted to reflect the character's intentions and level of conviction. It is also important to envisage how the audience may interpret the characters actions and words. By considering all these factors, animators can create characters that communicate lying convincingly and clearly.

3. Lying Characters in Animated Feature Films

The discussion of the animated films Pinocchio, Aladdin, Mulan, Rango, and Zootopia, that all feature lying characters, which play a significant role in the storytelling, follows in chronological order. This chronological order also coincides with a growth in the depth of the character personalities, the manner the lies are embedded in the stories and the subtlety in which they are communicated to the audience. Further, a small excursion into the concept of the Facial Action Coding System (FACS) will follow as the discussion turns to 3D animated films. FACS influenced how animators approached 3D facial rigging and animation, and informed a more realistic understanding and approach to animated facial movements and expressions. The last and most expansive analysis of lying animated performances focuses on Zootopia, as this film includes various motivations for lying, and different ways in which the lying performance is expressed and integrated into the storytelling.

Pinocchio

The movie Pinocchio (1940) deals with the theme of telling the truth, and the use of deceitful characters is a key element of the film. Pinocchio's lies are revealed in his body language, facial expressions, and dialogues, though his lying behavior is most clearly represented through his iconic growing nose. Pinocchio's growing nose was not part of Carlo Collodi's original novel, but has risen to be the central visual metaphor in Disney's interpretation of the story. In Pinocchio's case, the lies are always very easy to identify and visually exaggerated. The acting is not subtle and the visual cue for Pinocchio's lying is very explicit. Other characters such as the Fox and the Cat also deceive Pinocchio in order to take advantage of him for their own gain. The animation of their body language and facial expressions is also exaggerated, yet, more natural. None of the other characters features a similar visual cue as Pinocchio when they are lying.

In later animated films, a much more refined and realistic acting style develops. They begin to move away from the more cartoonish style of acting, and embrace a more sophisticated and realistic approach. This allows the characters to feel more human, with emotions and motivations that feel true to life. Comparing the Disney style from the 1940s to the 1979s, animator Andreas Deja writes, "The acting had changed, too. These animals often demonstrate nuanced, human behavior and the acting is much more subtle than in earlier Disney films". [6].

Aladdin

The 2D film *Aladdin* (1992) features several characters that use lying and deceit as a means of creating tension and conflict, among them the main protagonist Aladdin and the antagonist Jafar. Throughout the movie, Jafar lies and deceives Aladdin, his friends and the king to further his own agenda.

In the scene where Jafar responds to the king and tells him, “My life is but to serve you” (14:42), the body and facial acting is much exaggerated to show Jafar’s dishonesty. From a previously cunning expression, Jafar is performing a big bow, while his eyes are closed devoutly for an overly extended amount of time and his eyebrows are raised. The accent on the word “serve”, expressed by raising his eyebrows and looking up, is a further hint to his dishonesty and pretended loyalty. The overall exaggeration of his body poses and facial expressions shows the deceptive attitude of Jafar in this scene.

Aladdin himself lies to Jasmine about being a prince instead of a street boy. In the scene where Ali climbs on Jasmine’s balcony and introduces himself to her as a prince, the scene has two emotional beats. First, Ali states in a normal voice and with natural body and facial poses „it’s me, Prince Ali” (55:31), which shows the audience that this is a truthful expression, and that Ali shows his true personality. Then, after a short freeze and a look up, Ali clears his throat and repeats in a deeper voice „it’s me, Prince Ali Ababwa...” In this second part, Ali takes on exaggerated body poses that look rather artificial, as well as asymmetric facial expressions, to underline his fake personality and lie. Another undertone can be observed in these two beats. During the first beat, Ali believes in himself. Whereas in the second beat, we can deduct, that Ali himself does not believe in his fake prince personality.

Mulan

In the 2D animated film *Mulan* (1998), the titular character wants to save the life of her father by disguising herself as a man and joining the Chinese army in her father’s place. She lies to the soldiers in her unit, pretending to be a tough man and being able to fight. Her body language and facial expressions reveal her lies, as she often appears nervous and uncomfortable when she is trying to deceive the other characters. In a scene, Mulan shows off a supposed self-assured attitude and exaggerated “manly” behavior. Her commanding officer subsequently asks her, what her name is (33:30). As Mulan has not yet come up with a male cover name for herself, and is caught off guard by the question, she is pressured to make one up on the spot. She expresses her deception by contrasting behavior to her previous actions. Now she appears to shrink down physically. However, most explicit is her face and the eyes: she is averting her gaze; her eyes are looking down with several hasty eye darts searching for an answer. Once Mulan has recovered emotionally and focuses on lying about her name, she changes behavior again and starts to hold the gaze of the officer; now looking at him yet again self-assured, eyes locked on him and fewer changes in facial poses occur. In this scene, much of the behavior that indicates lying and deception is in the area of the eyes. There

are certain facial tells used in the scene that can be employed well with animated characters, such as raised eyebrows, averted eyes and rapid eye darts. *Lying is in the eyes*. As Jones and Oliff note, „the subtle motion of the eyes themselves can personify uneasiness, lying, or confusion” [7].

Rango

In the film *Rango* (2011), the chameleon protagonist lies and deceives his way through a variety of situations. The 3D animated film features an impressive amount of highly detailed and semi-realistic visuals, with great attention to realistic lighting and colors. The characters have a wide range of emotions, shown through their body movements and facial expressions. The fact that 3D is generally animated at 24 frames per second versus the predominantly 12 frames per second animation in 2D films, gives the 3D animation a more realistic feel. 3D animation is also a powerful tool for creating more detailed and realistic faces than what is usually possible with 2D animation. This is not only due to the frame rate of the animation, but also due to the workflow process and the precision of a 3D model, character rig and rendering. This enables animation teams to create more detailed facial features and subtle animations. Thus, the facial performance of a 3D character can be animated both in exaggerated and cartoony styles, as well as subtle and detail-rich with realistic emotions and expressions. Continuing changes in the narrative complexity and psychology of the stories and characters, that Andreas Deja has pointed out earlier, can also be seen in *Rango*. Similarly, the animated performance and emotional depth of the characters have equally matured.

In one scene, *Rango* tells a story about his past that is entirely fabricated. He is asked about Rattlesnake Jake, and being obviously scared and distracted by the mention of a snake, *Rango* lies about Jake being his brother (59:30). Before the lie, when *Rango* tries to come up with an answer, he is looking down and sideways and has frequent rapid eye movements. Once he utters the lie, *Rango*'s behavior changes again: he now looks straight at his audience holding the gaze and he has stopped fidgeting. Further, he reconfirms what he has said with exaggerated posing to mask his lie. Quite interestingly, after being asked how a lizard can have a snake as a brother, he answers: “Mama had an active social life”. This time, his reply is accompanied by eye darts and facial expressions that appear very natural and convey thought and truthfulness.

Facial Action Coding System (FACS)

In the field of psychology and behavior studies, Paul Ekman's research on facial expressions has brought forth the Facial Action Coding System (FACS). FACS describes the actions of individual muscles, called action units or AU. FACS does not code emotions. However, AUs or a combination of AUs let the observer describe, classify and compare the movement within facial expressions and associated emotions. This study into the structure of the muscles in the face and the resulting facial expressions has informed and furthered the complexity of contemporary high-end animated CG faces [8]. Whether for cartoon or realistic characters and

creatures, for animated features or high-end photorealistic VFX effects, the findings of Ekman's research and its absorption into character rigs and animation practice, has enabled the creation of heightened realism within the acting performance in faces.

Ekman's FACS support the understanding of the face, its structure and muscles, and its interpretation for animation. The artistic level of facial animations that can be created with CG animation has risen considerably, and subtlety and nuance in facial performances is sought after more frequently. To accurately capture and animate emotions, animators still need to continue to study real life facial expressions and body movements for a thorough understanding and interpretation. To animate lying characters, animators must pay close attention to behavior and tells commonly associated with lying. Examples of these expressions include avoiding eye contact, fidgeting and shifting body posture, and using facial expressions to mask or conceal feelings of guilt or shame. Additionally, facial expressions that accompany lies can often be very short-lived, so animators must pay close attention to the timing of these expressions in order to incorporate them into the facial performance.

Zootopia

In the movie *Zootopia* (2016) the main characters Judy Hopps and Nick Wilde are confronted with many deceitful characters; Nick himself being a frequent liar when he runs one of his frauds. The tension between truth and lies is a major source of conflict in the story and adds to the movie's overall suspense. Thus, many scenes show lying characters with various degrees of obvious or hidden deception in the acting performance. In addition, Judy often struggles to tell if someone is telling the truth or not. Most fascinating are the scenes in which the protagonists are lying to reach their objectives. In the scene in the elephant run ice cream shop, we see fox Nick Wilde accompanied by little Finn in an elephant costume. The owner refuses to sell ice cream to Nick, but Nick underlines his desire to buy in this shop with the line "my boy loves all things elephant" (19:15). Nick's acting is overall highly exaggerated, and his equally exaggerated facial expressions, in particular the raised eyebrows, are held still for a long period. This communicates to the audience (and the elephants in the shop), that Nick is deceptive and not entirely truthful: there is an ambivalence in his facial communication. However, Judy falls for his show and believes Nick. Thus, we can see in this scene that different conclusions can be drawn from witnessing Nick's acting performance: he can be both understood as a con artist or as a loving caring father desiring ice cream for his son. As Ekman and Friesen explain: "In a sense the face is equipped to lie the most and leak the most, and thus can be a very confusing source of information during deception" [9]. The ambiguity of convincing acting by Nick, mixed with some revealing tells such as overly exaggerated poses in face and body, is a wonderful introduction to Nick's skill in deception.

As the scene continues, Nick pushes his con of Judy even further by claiming he has forgotten his wallet (20:27) and putting on a fake search of his pockets. Once more, we see exaggerated acting and long held extreme facial expressions to communicate lying. While mentioning "wallet", Nick

performs a super exaggerated accent by opening his eyes and eyebrows very wide. Even though Judy has a built-in distrust of foxes, as seen in the beginning of the same sequence, she believes that Nick tells the truth in this scene. However, by now, the audience has understood that Nick is putting on a show, or to put it clearly - is lying - to get the ice cream; and now he is even getting Judy to pay for it, with a very blatant lie about forgetting his wallet. Nick continues his dialogue in the scene: "I'd lose my head if it weren't attached to my neck..." which he delivers truthfully and even adding "...that's the truth", playing further with the story theme of truth and lies.

Lying about Emotions

In the previous example, there were no emotional stakes involved. Nick's con was a purely economic endeavor. However, people lie for a range of reasons. Ekman, Friesen, and O'Sullivan have found differences depending on the motivation: "Facial expressions (and many vocal and bodily clues as well) are most likely to provide clues to deceit when the lie is about emotion, especially emotion felt at the moment of the lie. Even when the lie is not about feelings." [9]. According to Ekman, also feelings about lying may produce behavioural clues to deceit, such as the fear of being caught, the guilt about lying, or the pleasure of deceiving someone, also called duping delight [4].

This concept can be seen in action in the scene in which Judy's parents call her. They want to check in on her after her first day with the city police. Judy is frustrated just before the call comes in, but puts on a big smile for her parents. She tells them about her first day „it was real great“ (27:00). Judy lies about her emotions, but her parents are too distracted to notice it. Judy's response is showing clues to deception and leaks through her exaggerated long held extreme facial expressions, such as raised eyebrows and wide-open eyes, and a frozen smile. Thus, the audience can easily spot that she is lying.

Judy also does not show a so-called Duchenne smile, which is a truthful smile that includes natural contractions of the muscles around the eyes [8]. Even though Judy does have some contractions in the lower eyelid area during her fake smile, it appears frozen and unnatural, and far from a genuine happy smile.

The most complex scene regarding lies and deception takes place during the end of the movie. After Sheep Bellwether shoots Nick with the "blue poison" bullet, Nick attacks Judy and Judy retreats in fear (1:31:43). However, the entire attack is fake: the bullet is a blueberry and not filled with blue poison. This is a story point that the audience does not yet know. Nick fakes a wild attack on Judy and Judy in turn fakes fear. By now, Judy has become an accomplished liar and both the audience and Bellwether believe the attack is real. During the attack, Bellwether explains her entire scheme to them and Judy records her confession.

Interestingly, there are no tells for deception from either Nick or Judy in this fake attack sequence! The audience is not supposed to know that both are faking and acting the attack, and that the poison has not affected Nick. This is a rare moment in which the audience is also deceived and not "in" on the lie. This further heightens the suspense into a well-deserved climax, and a surprising resolution once the deception of Judy and Nick is revealed and the confession of Bellwether successfully obtained.

4. Conclusion: To Lie or Not to Lie - Clarity is Key

Animated acting and performance has evolved in its believability and in its richness in detail. Certainly, this also applies to the animation of lying and deceiving characters, whether they lie with their words, their bodies, their faces or all parts together. Ekman's research into lies also focuses on micro expressions. Micro expressions are flashes of concealed emotions on and off the face in less than one-quarter of a second [4]. However, micro expressions are hard to detect and animators and storytellers would risk that only a part of the audience could detect them, thus it is not quite feasible to use them in animation.

To serve the storytelling, there may not be any ambiguity about the feelings, intentions or deception of a character. Clarity is key in the communication with the audience [10]. Easily understandable facial acting in the animated characters performance is a main priority in successful storytelling. As shown in the acting analysis of the characters discussed, lies can be expressed by a multitude of animated behaviour. The characters in the films Pinocchio, Aladdin, Mulan, and Zootopia show their lies through performances with generally overly exaggerated facial expressions. In Mulan, Rango, and Zootopia, we see lies communicated by frequent, hasty eye darts, and exaggerated raised eyebrow poses that are often held over a longer period than usual. Lastly, a more subtle expression of a lie is the fake smile of Judy as seen in Zootopia, animated to show a lack of proper contractions around the eyes. No matter what choices animators and filmmakers make for their characters performance, the audience must always be able to understand clearly and without ambiguity what emotions, feelings and intentions are being communicated - or lied about.

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